

Development of an international system of education and professional training of specialists in the field of nuclear technologies for food and agriculture^{*}

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Abstract

The article presents the experience of training foreign students of Rosatom State Corporation's flagship universities at the MEPhI Resource Center. It is shown that over the period 2018–2024, more than 500 bachelor's, specialist and master's students from 33 countries studying at the five largest flagship universities of the state corporation (VSU, MEPhI, SPbPU, TPU, UrFU) underwent practical training in English and Russian at the Resource Center of Obninsk Institute for Nuclear Power Engineering (IATE MEPhI). Students were trained in six educational programs of 13 and 14 specialty groups. In the field of non-energy application of nuclear technologies, practice-oriented training at the Resource Center is carried out to a greater extent on radiation technologies in agriculture and the food industry. High results of cooperation in training foreign students in the field of agro-nuclear technologies between the IATE MEPhI and the National Research Center "Kurchatov Institute" – RIRAE were noted. Practical training of students at RIRAE is carried out on a unique gamma-installation GUR-120 for irradiation of agricultural raw materials and food products for the purposes of phytosanitary and microbiological safety, increase in shelf life, radiation stimulation. The competencies acquired by students in the field of agricultural radiation technologies are in demand by them when applying for jobs in the Centers of Nuclear Science and Technology. The interaction of the Resource Center of the IATE MEPhI and the leading research institutes of Obninsk in training foreign students is the basis for the development of the international scientific and educational center "Obninsk Tech" for training personnel for foreign businesses of the State Corporation "Rosatom" in the nuclear industry and related areas of application of nuclear technologies.

Keywords

State Corporation "Rosatom", flagship universities, education export, development of human resources, Obninsk Tech, professional training, practice-oriented approach, resource center, agricultural radiation technologies

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Introduction

In his work (Leipunsky 1968), more than 55 years ago, A.I. Leipunsky formulated the idea that nuclear physics will lead in future to the evolution of not only large and small nuclear power, but will also give impetus to the development of radiation technologies in related fields of science: “will make it possible to desalinate water, inspect radiographically products using isotope sources, sterilize medical instruments and materials, preserve food products, use isotopes for therapy, handle polymers, etc.” All these scientific applications have been embodied in Obninsk where major scientific and educational centers of an international level were formed in addition to the Institute of Physics and Power Engineering (established in 1946), the world leader in nuclear power, radiation material testing and radiopharmaceutical production:

- Obninsk Institute for Nuclear Power Engineering (IATE) of the National Research Nuclear Center MEPhI (higher education in the field of nuclear power, nuclear medicine, radiopharmaceuticals, radiation safety, radiobiology), in 1953;
- A.F. Tsyba Medical Radiological Scientific Center of the National Medical Research Center of Radiology (nuclear medicine), in 1958;
- NPO “Typhoon” (radioecology, radiation safety), in 1958;
- L.Ya. Karpov Research Institute of Physical Chemistry (radiation chemistry, radiation material testing, radiopharmaceuticals), in 1959;
- Rosatom Technical Academy (further vocational education in the field of nuclear power), in 1967;
- National Research Center “Kurchatov Institute” – Research Institute of Radiology and Agroecology (radiation technologies in agriculture and food industry, radioecology), in 1970.

Since 1953, manpower has been trained for nuclear power plants in the USSR and, later, in Russia, the research institutes in Obninsk and domestic scientific applications of nuclear technologies by the MEPhI – the Obninsk Institute for Nuclear Power Engineering (IATE), which plays the role of a scientific and educational innovation center in the interests of high-technology industries and, primarily, Rosatom State Corporation. As the core university within the MEPhI, the IATE currently trains personnel for:

- Russian and foreign NPPs (including NPPs with small reactors);
- nuclear science and technology centers (NSTC) in Russia and other countries, GMP plants;
- nuclear medicine, jointly with the National Medical Research Center of Radiology, the Federal Medical and Biological Agency, Rosatom facilities, and the National Research Center “Kurchatov Institute”.

In recent years, the IATE has actively been engaged in training foreign students for Rosatom’s international projects. Thus, to an order from Rosatom, there were three

major productions of nuclear specialists at the IATE: in 2017 (for the Socialist Republic of Vietnam), in 2018 (for the Republic of Turkey and Mongolia), and 2020 (for the People’s Republic of Bangladesh and the Plurinational State of Bolivia). Currently, there are over 450 students of 67 countries trained at the IATE. Based on the extensive experience of the IATE in training foreign specialists, a decision was made at the August 2023 meeting of the President of the Russian Federation V.V. Putin and Director General of Rosatom State Corporation A.Ye. Likhachev to establish, based on the IATE and jointly with scientific centers and innovative enterprises in Obninsk, an international nuclear education cluster (Meeting with the head of the State Corporation Rosatom Alexey Likhachev 2023). The Obninsk Tech international education center in the field of power engineering and related nuclear technologies currently in the process of establishment will aim at providing high quality training for Russian and foreign specialists, as well as to support the country’s manpower sovereignty for the evolution of the Russian Federation’s high-technology and knowledge-intensive industries. The key component of Obninsk Tech is the methodology center aiming to individualize the educational tracks for students at Rosatom’s core universities, which shape personal training strategies, taking into account orders from industries, the level and modularity of progress in disciplines, and the needs and psychological peculiarities of students.

As part of training personnel in engineering of non-energy nuclear technologies, alongside nuclear medicine, much attention is given to agricultural radiation technologies. Practical application of these requires knowing the fundamentals of radiobiology of microorganisms, plants and animals, proficiency in design and maintenance of irradiation equipment, as well as skills in using modern computational and experimental methods of ionizing radiation monitoring.

The purpose of this paper is to review the experience of interaction between the IATE and the NRC “Kurchatov Institute” – RIRAE in training of foreign students in the field of using radiation technologies in agriculture and food industry as part of developing the Obninsk Tech International Nuclear Education Center.

Role of the IATE’s resource center in foreign specialist training

In addition to large and small nuclear power, Rosatom State Atomic Energy Corporation has expanded greatly the use of nuclear science and technology in a variety of fields other than concerned with energy generation. Thus, Rosatom’s JSC Rusatom Overseas is engaged in exporting Russian nuclear technologies to friendly countries under the RIVER (Research Innovative VERSatile Reactor) brand. This innovative product for non-energy application of nuclear technologies includes a number of alternative solutions tailored to the customer needs. For instance, a multipurpose irradiation center, a part of the Center for Research and Development in Nuclear Technologies (CRDNT) at El Alto, the

Plurinational State of Bolivia, was designed, jointly with the RNC “Kurchatov Institute” – RIRAE, by the Research Institute of Technical Physics and Automation, JSC (NIIT-FA) and the State Specialized Design Institute, JSC (GSPI), Rosatom’s scientific centers. In 2023, the multipurpose irradiation center and the integrated preclinical cyclotron and radio pharmacology facility were put into operation. These two CRDNT modules are used now to produce radiopharmaceuticals (technetium-99, fluoroglucose) and radiologically sterilize agricultural products, cosmetic raw materials, medical products and pharmaceuticals to protect them against pathogenic bacteria, fungi and viruses. The Center’s gamma ray production facility will treat radiologically agricultural and food products with over 70 tons to be processed daily, as well as medical products (Strana Rosatom 2024).

Successful operation and evolution of the Bolivian CRDNT requires trained personnel. Russia provides comprehensive support to Bolivian counterparts in education of Bolivian students and vocational training of personnel. An educational program has been currently under way in Russia to train Bolivians in nuclear and associated fields at Rosatom’s core universities (Panov and Koz’min 2022). Over the past six years, 132 Bolivian students have undergone

training in Russia. Back at home, they have been prestigiously employed within the CRDNT and will use their knowledge for the scientific development of Bolivia.

An important role in training personnel for nuclear power plants and the Centers for Research and Development in Nuclear Technologies is played by the MEPhI’s Resource Center based at the MEPhI’s three regional universities: IATE in Obninsk, VITI in Volgodonsk, and NVPI in Novovoronezh. The VITI and NVPI resource centers have their focus on training personnel for nuclear power plants, and IATE, in addition, trains personnel for non-energy fields in interaction with the scientific centers in Obninsk. Specific to all three sites of the Resource Center is primarily a practice-oriented approach to training, which comprises all types of practical training programs including academic, on-the-job, production and pre-graduation training. Over the past seven years, more than 500 foreign students of 33 countries have taken practical training courses at IATE’s Resource Center as part of their training programs at Rosatom’s five largest core universities (Table 1). Undergraduate, specialist’s degree and master’s program students take Russian- and English-language practical training courses as part of six academic programs (groups 13 and 14 of training programs).

Table 1. Practical training of foreign students at IATE 2018–2024

Scientific center	Rosatom’s core university	Training program	Country	Year	Number of students
IPPE	MEPhI	13.04.01 Thermal Power & Heat Engineering 13.04.02 Electrical Power Engineering & Electronics	Azerbaijan	2018	81
			Armenia		
			Afghanistan		
			Bangladesh		
			Bolivia		
			Botswana		
			Vietnam		
			Ghana		
			Egypt		
			Zambia		
			India		
			Indonesia		
			Jordan		
			Kazakhstan		
RIPC	TPU	14.03.01 Nuclear Power Engineering & Thermal Physics	Cambodia	2019	132
MRSC	SPbPU	14.03.02 Nuclear Physics & Technologies	Kenia	2020	122
			Kirghizia	2021	28
NRC KI	UrFU	14.03.02 Nuclear Physics & Technologies	Congo	2022	26
			Lebanon	2023	44
NPO Typhoon	VGU	14.04.01 Nuclear Power Engineering & Thermal Physics 14.04.02 Nuclear Physics & Technologies	Macedonia	2024	74
			Mongolia		
			Nigeria		
			Ruanda		
			Serbia		
			Syria		
			Sudan		
			Tanzania		
			Turkey		
			Uganda		
			Uzbekistan		
			Czech Republic		
			Ethiopia		
			Republic of South Africa		
Total	5	6	33	7	507

The following algorithm is used to train Russian and foreign students at the IATE's Resource Center: order for personnel from Rosatom State Corporation → training at Rosatom's core universities → practical training at the Resource Center → scientific centers in Obninsk. By now, most of the practical courses have been organized jointly with the NRC "Kurchatov Institute" – RIRAE in the field of agronuclear technologies, which allows generalizing the experience of interaction between the scientific and educational centers.

Development of ANTs in Russia and worldwide

The possibilities for using ionizing radiation to treat radiologically agricultural raw materials and food products have been explored since the 1940s (Kaushansky and Kuzin 1984). Later, respective national programs were developed in a number of the world's leading countries where radiation technologies (RT) were being developed rapidly, and an International Program was signed in 1970 to undertake such research. The establishment of an interstate advisory body was initiated further for research on radiation technologies for food industry by the FAO, the WHO and the IAEA, the United Nation's key structures in this field of science (The Codex Alimentarius. General Standard for Irradiated Foods 2007). The investigation results have shown that RTs allow reducing greatly spoilage of meat, fish, fruit and vegetables in the process of transportation and lengthening markedly their storage period. At the same time, this cuts the overall electricity cost and the need for using large amounts of preservation agents. Irradiated food products do not contain high concentrations of harmful chemicals and have their

organic structure undamaged due to no heat treatment (Radiation technologies in agriculture and food industry 2015). The key characteristics of the RTs used in farming and food industry are presented in Table 2.

According to the IAEA data, interest has recently grown greatly worldwide to using RTs in farming and food industry. Thus, as many as 70 countries have already introduced regulations that permit irradiation of over ninety types of agricultural and food products. In recent decades, RT markets have seen a rapid growth in Southeast Asian and South American countries (Ihsanullah 2014) where fruit irradiation technologies are regionally essential so that to slow down fruit ripening and disinfestation process needed for export supplies.

In China, where RTs have evolved extensively for many years, 18 standards had been developed and introduced by the mid-1990s to irradiate different types of farm produce. The People's Republic of China, as part of its active cooperation with the FAO/IAEA center, has currently begun to use radiologically induced selection to breed new crop varieties. One of these is Luyuan 502, a drought and disease resistant wheat variety with an 11% higher yield compared to traditional wheat varieties. There are currently over 3.8 million ha seeded with Luyuan 502 in China (At the forefront of science for food and agriculture 2021).

On a permanent basis, there are 12 types of food products irradiated in Indonesia, and 26 and 18 food product types irradiated in South Korea and Bangladesh respectively (Ihsanullah 2014). Over the past decade, radiation treatment of agricultural raw materials and food products was approved in Mongolia, Malaysia, Nepal, Myanmar and the Eurasian Union countries (Radiation technologies in agriculture and food industry 2015). The data presented show that there is interest in using RTs in farming and food industries worldwide, and given the steady growth in

Table 2. Competences of radiation technologies depending on ionizing radiation dose characteristics (Radiation technologies in agriculture and food industry 2015, Nemenushchaya LA 2015) [7, 8]

Competence	Dose (kGy)	Irradiated products
Low dose (below 1 kGy)		
Stimulation of crop seeds	0.003–0.05	Crop seeds
Sprout inhibition for tuberous roots and bulbs packed for storage	0.03–0.15	Potato, onion, garlic, tuberous roots, ginger, etc.
Insect pest destruction	0.15–1.0	Grain, cereals, flour, nuts, oil crop and bean seeds, fresh and dried fruit and vegetables, dried fish, etc.
Fruit ripening inhibition	0.2–1.0	Fresh fruit
Average dose (1–10 kGy) (radicidation, radurization)		
Inactivation of certain pathogens and/or control of different parasitic organisms	0.1–3.0	Animal and vegetable food products
Shelf life extension by reducing the population of microorganisms causing food product spoilage	0.5–3.0	Fruit, vegetables, meat, minced meat, partially prepared food and ready meals
Inactivation of nonspore-forming bacteria (Salmonella, Campylobacter, Listeria) in fresh and frozen food	3–10	Fresh and frozen animal and vegetable food products
Sterilization and improvement of food processing properties, reduction of drying and cooking time	3–10	Berries (increased juice extraction), dried vegetables (cooking time reduction)
Reduction of microorganism population in spices and other dried ingredients	3–10	Spices, dried food ingredients
High dose (10–60 kGy)		
Production of microbiologically safe food products using thermal inactivation and radiological sterilization after freezing	25–60	Meat, poultry, minced meat, ready meals, sterilized hospital diets

global population, in the context of the need for achieving the planet's food security, prospects will only be greater for agronuclear technologies. This requires a more developed network of scientific and production irradiation centers and a broad spectrum of personnel trained for such facilities.

Collaboration between the IATE and the RIRAE in training of personnel in agronuclear technologies

As part of establishing the Obninsk Tech International Scientific and Educational Center, issues involved in professional training of skilled personnel in the field of agronuclear technologies need to be addressed via a training infrastructure to be formed to achieve the university's close bond with Russian and foreign scientific and production RT centers and by consolidating experts in different fields for educational purposes.

The initial stage in implementing any agronuclear technology will primarily require radiation monitoring equipment and procedures and interactive software for the process of the ionizing radiation dose field formation to allow one to obtain online dose performance values for irradiated items. This makes it ultimately possible to identify the process regulations for irradiating different types of agricultural and food products. All information used to develop the model of dose fields for irradiated items is databased along with the NRC KI – RIRAE's long-term investigation and calculation data. As part of practical training, students are instructed how to use software in three areas (Denisova et al. 2018a):

- estimation of doses at a number of points within the irradiated item in a particular “radiation source –irradiation item” geometry;
- estimation of the radiation source and irradiated item characteristics with which the required dose level and rate are achieved at all points within the item in the process of irradiation;
- adjustment and optimization of the irradiation environment by moving irradiated items inside the irradiation room.

A code MCNP5 (MCNP 2003) is used for student training on the RNC KI – RIRAE basis. As a versatile code, MCNP5 is unrivalled among Monte Carlo radiation transport codes, specifically as it comes to problems involving a domain with a relatively small optical thickness (not more than 5 to 10 free path lengths). These include all nuclear medicine and radiobiology issues. A Monte Carlo multi-group photon data library is used as the data library (Denisova et al. 2018b).

A course of lectures and practical classes to train Russian and foreign students in using the MCNP5 code and experimental radiation monitoring methods using Fricke ferrous

sulfate dosimeters and ionizing radiation monitoring devices (Potetnya et al. 2021). In particular, the MCNP5 code and Fricke dosimeters are used to analyze comparatively calculated and experimental data on the dose field in the irradiation room of the GUR-120 facility (Dorn et al. 2024). Practical student training is based on the GUR-120 facility (NRC KI – RIRAE) intended for gamma ray irradiation of farm produce and food products. The GUR-120 comprises 8 irradiator blocks with the ^{60}Co radioisotope (total activity $4.47 \cdot 10^{15}$ Bq) (in “Scientific and technical infrastructure of the Russian Federation. Centers for the collective use of scientific equipment and unique scientific installations. Gamma radiation exposure unit GUR-120” (Scientific and technical infrastructure of the Russian Federation 2024)).

Proven regularities of the biological action of radiation form the basis for ANTs. As the natural radiation background is exceeded, a radiation-based hermetic effect takes place in the region of small exposure doses (Geraskin 1995). This, specifically, manifests itself as radiation stimulation of e.g., crop seeds (Koz'min et al. 2013; Churyukin and Geraskin 2017). Increasing the level of irradiation, when a mutagenic effect is achieved, allows one to use this factor for breeding to develop new varieties of crop plants (see Table 2). A higher exposure dose leads to the plant growth inhibition, which can be used to inhibit the tuber and fruit germination when in storage, as well as to sterilize pest insects. A further dose increase allows suppressing the growth of pathogenic organisms (Chizh et al. 2011). All these ANT applications are a part of the student practical training program.

During practical classes, students are introduced in most detail to irradiation of farm produce for sterilization purposes. The damaging effect of radiation is explained by the DNA of pathogens being damaged owing to the breakdown of their intermolecular bonds, and disorders in its synthesis and enzyme inactivation processes involved in the DNA damaged structure repair. Such processes are expressed in protein synthesis changes, cell phase cycling, chromosomal aberrations, increased frequency of mutations, and regulation system disorders leading to suppressed proliferation of microorganisms and even their death (Kudryashov 2004).

Practical classes are expected to give students knowledge of how food product irradiation can be used to increase the shelf life of partly prepared products, meat, fish and seafood (in doses of up to 7 kGy), root and tuberous crops (up to 0.15 kGy), fruit and berries (up to 3 kGy), and juices (up to 7 kGy) (General standard for foods treated with irradiated radiation 2003). Irradiation of meat with different types of ionizing radiation in a dose of 1 to 5 kGy allows making the shelf life at 0 to 5 °C several times longer while preserving the organoleptic characteristics and cooking properties of products (Isamov et al. 2017).

When in the process of practical training, students are introduced to results of investigating the effects ionizing radiation has on the evolution and proliferation of the Insect class representatives, which laid the basis for the development of RTs used to destroy insect pests in grains and grain

products, dried fruits, vegetables and food concentrates. The most promising approach is to use radiation treatment for the crop grain insect pest destruction, such as barn weevil, saw-tooth grain beetle and grain borer (Loy et al. 2016).

Important to practical classes is to focus the students' attention also on factors that make it difficult to introduce RTs into farming and food production. The most notable of these is radiophobia of the population that has increased many times since the accidents at the Chernobyl NPP in Ukraine and the Fukushima Daiichi NPP in Japan. As far as safety of irradiated food is concerned, it needs to be noted as part of discussions that natural radionuclides occur ubiquitously in nature, and we are permanently exposed to ionizing radiation effects. Such natural radionuclides, as ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and others, are encountered in food, water, human body and soil at places where we live and work. These isotopes define the natural radiation background in which all living organisms, including humans, feel safe. Photonuclear reactions in the process of radiological food treatment yield radionuclides with induced activity but their quantity is negligibly small, so the radiation level is more than 10 thousand times as low as the usual gamma background (Dosimetry for food irradiation 2002; Natural and induced radioactivity in food 2002).

A detailed practical ANT training program for bachelor's and master's program students, and the results of its implementation at the RNC KI –RIRAE are presented in Panov and Koz'min 2022.

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Conclusions

Due to being greatly promising, radiation technologies for agricultural applications require professional training of skilled personnel for irradiation centers in Russia and other countries. A possible way to address these issues is to involve the academic staff at universities in Russia's first science city of Obninsk (Obninsk had its science city status extended until 2040 on 26.07.2024) with its multidiscipline organizations and their areas of nuclear physical research (IPPE), procedural guidelines on ionizing radiation monitoring, development and application of radiation sterilization technologies (NRC “Kurchatov Institute”–RIRAE, MRSC, RIPC), development of technologies for radiological stimulation of crop seeds and radiological disinfestation, as well as innovative technologies based on combined effects of ionizing and ultraviolet radiation, non thermal plasma and a number of other electro physical factors (NRC “Kurchatov Institute”–RIRAE, IATE). The scientific, manufacturing and educational experience of the organizations concerned forms the basis in designing the laboratory facilities for the university campus of the Obninsk Tech international center for personnel training on nuclear and related nuclear technologies. Implementing this project will make it possible to establish a center not only for nuclear but also for multidiscipline education required for carrying out missions in non-energy applications of radiation technologies.

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